

Implementation of RSA Algorithm for Encryption and Decryption Recent Technology Trends in Computer Technology

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Abstract: *Cryptographic technique is one of the principal means to protect information security. Not only has it to ensure the information confidential, but also provides digital signature, authentication, secret sub-storage, system security and other functions. Therefore, the encryption and decryption solution can ensure the confidentiality of the information, as well as the integrity of information and certainty, to prevent information from tampering, forgery and counterfeiting. Encryption and decryption algorithm's security depends on the algorithm while the internal structure of the rigor of mathematics, it also depends on the key confidentiality. Key in the encryption algorithm has a pivotal position, once the key was leaked, it means that anyone can be in the encryption system to encrypt and decrypt information, it means the encryption algorithm is useless. Therefore, what kind of data you choose to be a key, how to distribute the private key, and how to save both data transmission keys are very important issues in the encryption and decryption algorithm. This paper proposed an implementation of a complete and practical RSA encrypt/decrypt solution based on the study of RSA public key algorithm. In addition, the encrypt procedure and code implementation is provided in details.*

Keywords: Cryptographic technique, Encryption and decryption

I. INTRODUCTION

NETWORKS are a must for any company to achieve competitive advantage; however, all communication over any network, mainly the Internet needs to be secure to prevent breach of confidential and sensitive data. An IBM sponsored benchmark study carried out by Ponemon Institute for the past 11 years highlights the alarming boost (see Fig. 1) in the average cost of data breach globally (ACoDBG) each year with 2016 being \$4 million, a 29 percent increase since 2013.

Networks aren't just used by businesses but also by home users. Hence, network security is of utmost importance. This brings in cryptography, as a major component enabling secure communications over networks. Cryptography looks at methods of hiding the actual message from unintended recipients by scrambling the data via an algorithm. The first proven use of cryptography dates back to 1900 B.C, Ancient Egypt, when a document writer used irregular hieroglyphs (writing system using a combination of graphics, symbols and alphabet) while copying a document. Modern cryptography algorithms offer more security than the ancient ones and can be divided into 3 categories, namely secret key, public key and hash functions. The focus of this paper is public key cryptography (PKC) algorithm.

II. METHODOLOGIES

RSA PUBLIC KEY CRYPTOGRAPHY Known also as asymmetric encryption, PKC works on the concept of dual keys. While the recipients' public key is used to encrypt the message, the private key is used for decryption, so there is no need to share a secret key as required in secret key (symmetric) cryptography. PKC is largely used for authentication, non-repudiation, and key exchange. The most widely used PKC algorithm in the world today, Rivest, Shamir, and Adleman algorithm (RSA) is considered superlative in comparison with algorithms such as the symmetric key Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) (Ponemon 2014). and the asymmetric Goldwasser and Micali (GM) algorithms. Officially launched in 1977 and named with the surname initials of inventors Ron Rivest, Adi Shamir, and

Leonard Adleman, RSA is actually a set of two algorithms; key generation, the most complex part used to produce the public and private keys, and RSA function evaluation which looks at encrypting and decrypting (Ponemon 2013). Fig. 2 explains how the public and private key is generated. Fig. 4 shows the methods of encrypting plaintext and decrypting a ciphertext using the two keys.

Fig 1: Global average cost of data breach from years 2012 to 2016. Data from Ponemon Institute reports for the years 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015 and 2016

Fig 2: RSA Public Key and Private Key Generation Method

RSA Security Inc. had a 17 year hold on RSA algorithm patent from 1983 till its expiry in 2000, however, the company surprisingly released its claim on the patent two weeks before the expiry date, making RSA available to the public domain, prompting a major competitor, Baltimore Technologies into free giveaway of a version of its Key tools developer tool kit which uses RSA algorithm and had cost developers \$10,000 to \$20,000 until now (Balakrishnan *et al.*, 2016). The patent years saw more than 800 licensed customers and development of over 1,000 applications, including the likes of Microsoft Windows, Netscape Navigator, Intuit Quicken, Lotus Notes, PGP, Cisco Systems Inc., routers, credit cards, iPhone text messaging, making web connections, and hundreds of other products/services to protect trillions of transactions (Ponemon 2015).

Fig 3: RSA Encryption and Decryption Methods

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Looking at where RSA is being used today, let's take the example of Pretty Good Privacy in short PGP, a freeware created by Phil Zimmerman, providing encryption and authentication for e-mail and file storage applications across multiple platforms and it uses RSA algorithm for its key transportation. Many cloud service providers also use PKC for authentication. One example is Google's G Suite, a brand of cloud based services that has been rated as excellent on PGMags review in February 2017, has about 3 million paid customers including large companies such as Whirlpool and PricewaterhouseCoopers taking advantage of a collaboration ready office suite, a website, shared calendars, mail services, chat, video conferences, social media, real-time document collaborations, and many more. This service has encryption at numerous stages and is enabled by default for all customers.

Firstly, data access is enabled through Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS) encrypted tunnels, then it uses Perfect Forward Secrecy (PFS), for which Google made headlines in 2011 for being the first to enable this feature (Ponemon 2016) which scrambles data as it moves between their and other companies servers and it uses SSL (Secure Sockets Layer)/TLS (Transport Layer Security) for connectivity where the 256-bit TLS looks at the encryption enforcement policy which rejects all inbound and outbound mail from other mail servers if they don't use TLS. A common operation in IT is RSA signature verification and many protocols such as SSH, OpenPGP, S/MIME and SSL/TLS rely on it. SSL certificates are used to protect the online users' private and sensitive data. In its bids to up defenses against the growth in cryptanalysis, Google has upgraded the length of all its SSL certificates RSA encryption keys from 1024 to 2048 bits for validation and key exchange in 2013. SSL, initially developed by Netscape, delivers data security incrustated between internet-based communications protocol TCP/IP and application protocols such as HTTP, Telnet, Network News Transfer Protocol (NNTP), or File Transfer Protocol (FTP) by establishing an RSA key exchange during the SSL handshake between client and server to authenticate each end of the connection (Ponemon 2013). Moreover, RSA is used for employee verification in many organizations. Chip based smart cards use cryptographic algorithms to ensure security by checking the PIN code.

Some of these cards use RSA algorithms in combination with other algorithms. For instance, IDPrime MD 3811 smart cards, a single chip based dual-interface (contact and contactless ISO14443 interface) smart card developed by Gemalto is also compatible with the NFC standard already widely used by mobile devices today and is secured with both RSA and elliptic curves algorithms. Another example of Gemalto's cards is the IDPrime PIV (personal identity verification) card v1.55 that looks at improved identification and authentication of US Federal employees and contractors to access Federal amenities and was published as FIPS PUB – 201.

Another product that uses RSA is the RSA SecurID, a two-factor authentication technology used in high-security environments to protect network resources and can be hardware authenticator (a USB token, smart card, software application residing on your smartphone or key fob) and RSA authentication manager software based tokens. The authenticator generates passcodes/pin tokens which resets itself every 60 seconds making the previous token worthless. When trying to access a protected resource, users enter the passcode together with their username which are intercepted by the RSA authentication Agent and presented to the RSA SecureID system on the RSA authentication server which validates the pass code by running the same algorithm that was used to generate the passcode to check if their 8-digit output matches the one entered by the user along with the username before granting access to the remote server.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

One of the reason RSA has become most widely used is because it allows either of the two keys to encrypt a message and the opposite key to decrypt it, thus promising confidentiality, integrity, authenticity and non-reputability of data and electronic communications. It's important to note that a weak key generation will make RSA very vulnerable to attacks therefore care must be taken to ensure that two large random prime numbers are used to calculate the modulus, n , which will become the public key and the private key will consist of those two primes themselves. The effectiveness of RSA algorithm comes from the fact that it's difficult to computationally factor large integers into primes. Multiplying the two primes is easy but performing the reverse in the form of factoring is actually hard and gets even harder as the values of p and q gets bigger (J Jeba *et al.*, 2022).

Take for instance, the RSA Factoring Challenge enacted by RSA Laboratories in 1991, has many moduli still pending to be factored. On 12 December 2009, a 768-bit RSA modulus containing a 232 decimal digit number was factored by a total of 13 researchers over a span of two years using hundreds of parallel computers, a task equivalent to approximately 2000 years of computing on a single-core 2.2 GHz AMD processor. The larger the key length of the modulus, the more time it takes to be factored. The Federal Information Processing Standards Publication (FIPS PUB) 186-4 specifies three choices for the length of the modulus, n , to be 1024, 2048 and 3072 bits. RSA's strength lies in its key size, since it's not easy to factor large primes, however encrypting with larger modulus has certain negatives associated with it, particularly when dealing with mobile devices as it requires more computing power and battery resource usage for key generation thus impairing device performance (IBM 2020).

Most hardware and software in compliance with FIOS PUB 186-4 are moving from the first choice of key length to the second and are having a minimum of 2048 bits as being secure but with increase in computing power, more efficient factoring algorithms and advances in cryptanalysis techniques, the ability to crack these keys also increases. A major hurdle to RSA cryptosystems is the enabling company's inability to accept that a problem does exist in the key length and the unwillingness of upgrading to keep up with the computing power of the current and possible future devices. An example from the past highlights this negligence (McAfee 2019 and Verizon 2021).

Chosen in 1980s, and broken in 2000, a 320-bit RSA modulus for Carte Bleue, is surely a mark of severe ineffectiveness on the part of the organization that oversaw security for 33 million French credit cards. After 2 years of failed attempts to convince the company of the serious flaws, Serge Humpich, a 36-year-old engineer purchased some metro tickets with fake cards and sent prove to the credit card company in attempts to sell his idea, however he was convicted to 10 months suspended sentence. The use of acoustic cryptanalysis is another challenge looming over the security offered by cryptography. A team of researchers, including Adi Shamir, a co-inventor of RSA, carried out an acoustic cryptanalysis attack on the popular GnuPG software which is a complete and free implementation of the OpenPGP standards and have successfully determined a 4096-bit RSA key within an hour, using the sound generated by the computer during the decryption of some chosen cipher texts (Cybersecurity 2021).

V. CONCLUSION

Even though RSA is the most used cryptography algorithm today, it has certain limitations which need to be taken into consideration for RSA to continue to be the best and research has to be done into making RSA quantum resistant. There is a need now more than ever for studies to be conducted in the area of quantum encryption methods resistant to quantum computers as it will soon replace the current encryption systems. Development of qCrypt isn't enough, but it's a start. However, we need more research into quantum resistant encryption systems.

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